

Assessment of National Security and Female Inclusivity: Challenges for Nigerian Peacekeepers

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Abstract

The study examined assessment of national security and female inclusivity: challenges for Nigerian peacekeepers. The study adopts the mixed studies systematic review by deployed study that adopted different research design method such as quantitative, qualitative, review among others between years 2000 and 2021. The population, intervention, comparison, outcome and study (PICOS) framework were used to inform the search strategy and initial searches were conducted on the initiation of search process which commenced on February 12, 2021 and also repeated on December 06, 2021 so as to cover up for gaps of relevant resources especially during the course of the writing of and reviewing the study. The search phase identified 86 papers; only 6 papers were eventually considered through abstract analysis. The findings of the study revealed that for effective and sustainable national security to be achieved by the Nigeria peacemakers which include the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others, there is need for the inclusion of gender relation to better involve female personnel in national security matters. Hence, attaining sustainable development and national security would be a mirage in Nigeria and the various efforts to achieve sustainable national security would be futile like was achieved in the past strategies. To this end, this study recommended that the proportion of women intake in the various Nigeria Force recruit should be increased so as to give room for a majority of women in the society to contribute and play their role in ensuring national security.

Keywords: Gender, Security, Challenges, Nigeria, Peacekeeping

Introduction

Security issues have been common phenomena at the local, national, regional and global levels hence, in trying to maintain peace and harmony in the society, stakeholders such as governments, policy makers, international organizations, security agents, among others have tried to ensure effective security. Hence, every nation ensures security from terrorism, crime, economic, political, homeland, energy, environment, food, and cyber related issues hence national security (Holmes, 2015). The concept of security has been noted to be a very complex issue hence, several definitions have been provided to it but the concept definition should cut across several of the arms of the nation which include human, economic energy, environment, food, and cyber related issues. For example, Osisanya (2022) noted that national security is the ability of a state to provide protection and defend its citizens. National security could also be defined as the security and defence of a sovereign state which also includes the citizens, economy, and institutions, which is regarded as a duty of government. It is also defined as the requirement to maintain the survival of the state by using powers which cuts across the economic, diplomacy, projection and political powers (Science Daily, 2022). According to Paleri (2008); Orhero (2020) and Uzodimma (2020), national security is the capability of a nation to overcome the multi-dimensional threats to the apparent well-being of its people and its survival as a nation-state at any given time, by balancing all instruments of state policy through governance and is extendable to global security by variables external to it. National security has two facets and include the external and internal (Paeri, 2008; Uzodimma, 2020). The external security involves the security challenges that originate from outside while those generated within the nation are termed internal security issues. Tackling these two forms of security are germane to national development.

In Nigeria, national security is a major challenge (Epron, 2018; Nwagboso, 2018). Despite the fact that Nigeria has the biggest economy in Africa and among the biggest in the world, security challenges have been a major problem affecting the nation's economy and there have been no clear-cut policies in place to address this high level of security problems in the nation. There are several incidences of insecurity issue in ritual killings, religious and political killing, cyber-crimes, car theft, carjacking, advanced free fraud, drug trafficking, human trafficking, terror-attacks by Islamic extremists in Jos and the North East, frequent clashes between farmers and herdsmen in the North-Central among others. Consequently, these security challenges have posed elastic threats to the nation's corporate existence and also undermined the quest for solidarity and unity in diversity in Nigeria (Nwagboso, 2018; Epron, 2019). Olufemi (2015) and Epron (2019) noted that several efforts have been

Assessment of National Security ... (Ekuerhare, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666782>

put in place to manage Nigeria security issues by the government to curb this menace, but to no avail. Among such efforts are the deployments of several Nigerian security agencies who are made to ensure peace in the society such as the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others to tackle these recurring security challenges (Momodu, 2019; Yake, 2019; Johnson, 2019; Owonikoko & Ashindorbe, 2019).

Also, several factors were responsible for the national security challenge such as poor system of governance, concession of political power to certain ethnic and religious group, religious fanaticism, injustice, weak judicial system, nepotism, bribery and corruption, wrong use of resources, unemployment and poverty, among others (Usman & Mathew, 2014). Also, according to Jacoby (2018), another important factor that could influence national security is gender relations. Gender relations is the social relationships and power distribution between men and women in both the society which include in the private (personal) and public spheres (UNDP RBEC, 2007; Orhero, 2020). It spelt out how people tend to interact with others and how others relate to them, depending on their attributed gender in connection within the cultural context in which they develop. Hence, it intersects with all other influences on social relations which are age, ethnicity, race, religion, among others to determine the position and identity of people in a social group. Therefore, gender relations are approached as a social construct hence can be transformed over time to become more equitable. Nearly every dimension of national security such as human, economic, energy, environment, food and cyber related issues (Holmes, 2015; Osisanya, 2022) is attached to the level of empowerment given to women (Navone, 2021). It was affirmed that for every suppression of the women in any society or nation, there is twice the chance of being a fragile state with 50% increased chance of becoming an unstable and violent society and one and half times the chance of experiencing terrorism (Navone, 2021). However, several communities such as the Nigeria society fail to understand gender relations issues and its connection to national security. The Nigerian force has more than 223,000 active personnel, and is one of the largest uniformed combat services in Africa, the fourth-most powerful military in Africa, and was ranked the 35th at the international level (Global Firepower, 2022). Not much is known about the population of female in the Nigerian army force.

However, Madobi (2022) noted that sustainable national security is not possible without the involvement of women. Hence, with growing evidences of gender issues in the communities of Nigeria (Omiunu, 2014), it is highly important to draw attention to the fact that ensuring complete and sustainable national security may be a challenge. The gender equality bill which was introduced in the Nigerian senate was given little or no publicity (Wole-Abu, 2018). But the Nigerian Armed forces have not recognise women as a major segment of the population or forces to contribute to the defence and security of the nation in order to ensure sustainable national security in Nigeria (Alaga, 2011; Ozemoya, 2017). According to Egbefo and Salihu (2014) and Obi (2015), a society without security threat is a dead society because it has been known as the reality of human existence and hence an important way to understand social behavior of a society. Also, the experience of women with regards to security issues remain an important subject for studies and on gendered relations but there is still a concentration of its effect to addressing security issues towards national transformation (Tickner 1995; Niethamme, 2020). Hence, several theorists contend that the “institution of war could be closely related to gender (Francis 2004). Therefore, there is need to examine the link between gender relations and national security with focus on the challenges among the Nigerian peacekeepers.

The concept of national security has been a very difficult issue at the local, national, regional and global levels (Egbefo and Salihu, 2014; Orhero, 2020) and has long been a major concern and attracted attention in various studies and countries (Habtamu, 2013; Orhero, 2020). Generally, two major sources of insecurity exist and include: remote factors, and immediate and proximate factors (Achumba, Ighomeroho and Akpor-Robaro, 2013; Nigeria – South Africa Chamber of Commerce (NSACC), 2023). Examples of remote factors include the lack of institutional capacity which has resulted to government failure; persistent material inequalities and unfair treatment in the society; ethno-religious conflicts; public and government conflicts; weak security system; loss of socio-cultural and shared value system; among others. Examples of immediate and proximate factors include porous borders; rural/urban drift; social irresponsibility of companies; unemployment/poverty; terrorism; among others. National insecurity is a major issue in Nigeria fuelled by the increased crime rate and terrorists attacks in different parts of the country, leaving unpalatable consequences for the nation’s economy and its growth (Ewetan and Urhie, 2014; Obi, 2015). Nwagboso (2018) noted that such threats and challenges could distort the socio-political and economic balance of the nation.

Ensuring and effective national security is not possible without the involvement of women in the national security peacekeepers such as the (Madobi (2022) which are the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others (Momodu, 2019; Yake, 2019; Johnson, 2019; Owonikoko & Ashindorbe, 2019). But Ozemoya (2017) affirmed that among the peacemakers in Nigeria, the place of

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women as a major segment of the population or forces to contribute to the defence and security of the nation in order to ensure sustainable national security in Nigeria is underestimated. In addition, even in the society, there are growing evidences of gender discrimination issues (Omiunu, 2014). Moreover, the gender equality bill was introduced in the Nigerian senate but was given little or no publicity (Wole-Abu, 2018). This could challenge the tendency to ensure complete and sustainable national security because according to Madobi (2022), national security can't be attained without women involvement in the national security peacekeepers. Moreover, studies on national security especially in Africa, Nigeria inclusive, have focused on providing explanations for the deterioration of national security and tend to focus on the causes with interest drawn to contradictions of globalization and identity-based struggles for control of power and resources, simultaneous economic and also the national political reforms, flawed democratization, the declining state capacities and also the diminishing resources and proliferation of small arms (Hendricks, 2011; Nigeria – South Africa Chamber of Commerce (NSACC), 2023; Orhero, 2020). Much of these studies do not consider gender related issues such as the gender relations as a specific factor that could influence national security. Therefore, there is need to examine the link between gender relations and national security with focus on the challenges among the Nigerian peacekeepers.

Methodology

The study adopts a mixed studies systematic review with focus on the research objective of the study. The mixed studies systematic review focuses on the use of several studies that deployed different research design method such as quantitative, qualitative, review, among others due to the lack of studies that focus on this study. Systematic review is branch of review design that focuses on the deployment of systematic methods to collect and appraise data and information obtained from secondary sources such as databases of publishers, television websites, and other publications. It is designed to enumerate and provide a complete and exhaustive summary of current evidence (Giang et al., 2019). In addition, the major search engines used to search for materials are the google scholar and the google search engines. Also, the Cochrane reviews style was deployed for the reviewing of the literature as stated by Sieving (2007) and Chapman (2014). Also, the PICOS framework was used to inform the search strategy (Huang et al., 2006). The PICOS acronym represents (Richardson,1995): P –Problem or Population; I – Intervention; C – Comparison, control or comparator; O – Outcome(s); S - Study type (e.g. randomized controlled trial, cohort study, etc.). With regards to this study, the PICOS framework used is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. PICOS

	Inclusion	Exclusion	Search terms
Population	Gender issues in national security	Other national issues	Gender relations and National Security: Challenges for the Nigerian Peacekeepers
Intervention	None	None	None
Comparator	None	None	None
Outcome	National Security		National Security in Nigeria Role of peace makers Women peace makers
Study type	Mixed studies systematic review	None	Mixed studies systematic review

The initiation of searching process commenced February 12, 2021 and this was also repeated on December 06, 2021 so as to obtain wide elastic relevant resources that have not been previously covered in the previous date especially in the process of writing of and also reviewing the paper. Mixed studies were all considered and adopted in this study and materials deployed include those within the years 2000 and 2021. Also, the PRISMA Flow Diagram for the study search is provided in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: The PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Study

Source: The Author

To ensure effective materials appraisal in this study, several components were inculcated such as the evaluation of the appropriateness of the study design that was used in the study, the methodological features of such design, the author of the article; sources of the articles, among others. Moreover, to further synthesize the information retrieved, data extraction was deployed but this was revolved around the research objective and questions of the study as stated by Frederiksen (2017).

Results and Discussion

The study focused on examining gender relations and national security: challenges for the Nigeria peacekeepers, and the results and discussions were provided. The search phase identified 86 papers; only 6 papers were eventually considered through abstract analysis. The analyses of these papers are presented below. The United Nations (2022), in trying to ensure the attainment of Goal 5 which is achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls, revealed that in certain geographical locations such as Nigeria, the discriminatory laws and social norms remained pervasive as women in the society which could also include those involved in peacemaking are underrepresented. Although, it also noted that certain progress to this effect has been made in the last decades as more women are serving in parliament and positions of leadership, and certain laws are subjected to reformation to ensure gender equality which could cut across the peacemakers of the national security in Nigeria. In other sectors of the economy, women have play disproportionate roles as healthcare workers, careers at home and a large percentage of women work in the formal and informal economy, which tend to contribute to national development in the long run. Hence, they could also be of major significance in ensuring national security. This concurs with the findings of Jacoby

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(2018), that gender relations hold a prominent place in ensuring national security. Ozemoya (2017) wrote about gender equality in Nigeria: implications of the national defense policy, as noted that despite the roles of great women in the Nigerian society such as the Queen Amina of Zaria, Queen Idia of the Benin Kingdom, among others, the Nigerian military does not include female intake in the regular combatant cadet. Only the Regular Combatant Commission are allowed to enhance career growth and are provided the opportunity to head in any of the Nigerian services up to the rank of the Chief of Defense Staff. Hence, because women are not allowed in the intake in the regular combatant cadet, women may not be able to move on career path and may not have the opportunity to head any of Nigerian services and cannot move to the rank of the Chief of Defense Staff. Moreover, underestimating the role of women in advancing national interests such as national security could affect development. Hence, gender equality should govern not only the ranks of the defense service but also the philosophy of advancement in true equality and equity in Nigeria. This concurs with the works of Alaga (2011) and Ozemoya (2017) that the Nigerian Armed forces have failed to recognise women as a major force to contribute to the defence and security of the nation.

Alaga (2011) examined gender and security policy in West Africa, and found that threats to security in West Africa are largely intra state in nature and rendering the State and military centered security almost irrelevant. The study revealed that there is a gender aspect to national security which demands the analyses of gender dimensions with regards to national security challenges. Also, the military and the entire security sector which include the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others as stated by Momodu (2019); Yake (2019); Johnson (2019); Owonikoko and Ashindorbe (2019), among others should put into consideration gender related approach to better deliver accountable security to the citizens and the state.

Oluremi (2021) examined women, peace and security in Nigeria through the domestic and international legal framework, and revealed that the issue related to national security is a global phenomenon due to its strategic importance to the national progress hence, no nation dire treat national security with levity. Despite the place of national development at the global level and the position women hold, also at the global level, women have not been given the full and equal opportunity in ensuring peace building in Nigeria due to several factors such as discrimination, patriarchy, culture, lack of legal framework, and others. The study of Oluremi (2021) revealed that women are powerful agents for peace and security in various societies and the nation at large and have the capability to engage in various areas of the nation for peace coalition. Therefore, there is the need for the adoption of gender perspective to peace building and involvement of women, towards imbuing them in the national security plans and strategies towards ensuring better security outcome in the nation.

The need to reconsider gender relations in national security is hinged on the fact that women are targeted and vulnerability and at the same time have strengths made women to be included in conflict prevention, peacemaking and building. The study also revealed that women have in the past acted as peace builder in major civil/uncivil war. Women support war efforts in multiple ways such as: they resist and fight, are not neutral bystanders during conflict. The study also revealed that integrating gender issues into the security sector is a major phenomenon at the formulation of peace agreements, participatory national dialogues and constitutional and electoral reform processes hence, the need to tackle the persistence of gender biases, the lack of educational and training opportunities for women, lack of a quota system for women, influence of cultural attitudes that have worked against women deployment in ensuring peacekeeping, women-unfriendly equipment and uniform design and living quarters, lack of role models, among others. Hence, with the high number of active force personnel in Nigeria, and the fourth-most powerful military in Africa, and the 35th at the international level as stated by Global Firepower (2022), not given priority to women in the national security plan and strategy may lead to gender bias and also may not ensure sustainable national security as stated by Madobi (2022) coupled with the growing evidences of gender issues in the Nigerian society as stated by Omiunu (2014). Hence, this justifies the assertion of Wole-Abu (2018) that the gender equality bill introduced in the Nigerian senate was given little or no publicity.

Idike, Okeke, Okorie, Ogba & Ugodulunwa (2020) examined gender, democracy, and national development in Nigeria, and revealed that national development has been stunted in Nigeria because of gender related issue particularly the unequal gender representation across the nation and in several of the Armed Forces arms of the nation. Also, their result revealed that the existing male-prone gender representation in Nigeria have only led to increasing in poverty and underdevelopment. To this end, Nigerian women could use powers inherent hence, should be included in the various arms of the nation's economy, particularly in the security issues of the nation. The result revealed that gender approach to security denotes that security must be connected to empowerment hence, women empowerment and involvement in the national security becomes germane. This also bolsters the findings of Jacoby (2018) and Navone(2021), that gender relations holds a prominent place in ensuring national security. Hence, the Nigeria peacemakers which include the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others as stated by Momodu (2019); Yake

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(2019); Johnson (2019); Owonikoko and Ashindorbe (2019), among others should inculcate gender relations in achieving national security.

Conclusion

In conclusion, for effective and sustainable national security to be achieved by the Nigeria peacemakers which include the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Police Force, Military Joint Task Forces, the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps, Nigerian Prisons Service, among others, there is need for the inclusion of gender relation to involve females; hence, attaining sustainable development and national security would be a mirage in Nigeria and the various efforts to achieve sustainable national security would be fruitless like was achieved in the past strategies.

Recommendations

1. The proportion of women intake in the various Nigeria Force recruit should be increased so as to give room for a majority of women in the society to contribute and play their role in ensuring national security.
2. Women should also be inculcated into the regular combatant cadet intake so as to also have the opportunity for career growth and development towards been able to obtain the Chief of Defense Staff to be able to contribute their quota to national security.
3. Also, there is need for other women empowerment and social restructuring for women to be involved in the national security of Nigeria.
4. Also, there should be need for providing other measures such as short service opportunity and other courses that could also empower women in the Nigerian Force to be able to contribute and play their role in ensuring national security.

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